
MODERN THEORIES OF LEADERSHIP AND TYPES OF LEADERS

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Abstract

Globalization has opened the borders of countries, due to which the competition between the companies intensified it became necessary to guide and manage not the usual a manager, but a globally minded manager or leader. Even today, the question of the phenomenon of leadership is controversial among scientists about, in particular, how should he be a leader, with qualities or skills, whether it is possible to learn leadership, etc.

Cross-Country Perceptions of Leadership Skills and Traits is different. There are different views on it in terms of vertical management hierarchy and network structuring. of business network structures clearly influence organizational culture he showed us about the leader and leadership.

In such conditions, when Georgia is also one of the members of the global world, in relation to the compatibility of Georgian culture, the issue of how it should be in Georgia should be studied the leader of a functioning company, what qualities and skills should have, what features of Georgian culture should he grasp and, finally, what should he be able to give for the success of the company "As a victim".

The world is changing at lightning speed and also at lightning speed public interest in leadership and leaders is growing. We all have a certain view of what leadership is, however the exact definition of the term is still difficult. Some scientists believe that leadership is the result of successful group dynamics, Others believe that leadership is determined by the grandiose efforts of a person. There is also an opinion that the leader is influenced by circumstances and necessity creates, however, according to another opinion, leadership a person with qualities is always a leader.

It is important to understand that the leadership style or type used by managers or leadership positions in a company always has consequences for workers, even if we do not realize it or confuse these consequences with the inner personality of each person. It is very important to clarify this, since leaders are agents who believe that they are in a privileged position to influence others for better or worse.

Keywords: Management, Leadership, Georgia

Modern approaches to Management

American businessman, founder of Microsoft company and CEO (Gates, Bill, n.d.)rightly notes: "We expect that in the next century, the leader will be the one who makes others authorized".

Transformational leadership is one of the most modern and popular leadership theories. It was founded in the 80s of the 20th century and is "part of the new leadership paradigm" (Peter Guy Northouse, 2010). The theory was based on the works of (Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. ., 2006) (Burton Nanus, Warren G. Bennis, 2006) made important contributions to the development of the theory. According to (Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. ., 2006), the popularity of transformational theory is likely due to its emphasis on intrinsic motivation and follower development. According to this theory, people at the level of change and uncertainty need inspiration and faith in themselves. In their (2001) analysis of articles published in the Quarterly Journal of Leadership, Lue and Gardner concluded that 1/3 of the studies were about transformational or charismatic leadership. Transformational leadership is one of the most comprehensive theories. This is a process that leads to changes and transformations in people. It deals with emotions, values, ethics, standards and long-term goals. Also, it includes evaluation of followers' motivation. meeting their needs and treating them with respect. According to this theory, leaders inspire and motivate followers to do great things and hold followers to high standards. According to this approach, the leader must understand and adapt his actions to the

needs and motives of the followers. In transformational leadership, pseudo-transformational leadership is distinguished, which transforms in a negative way. Leaders who experience transformation in a negative way, are self-absorbed, focused on power and are carriers of distorted moral values are considered pseudo-transformational.

Transformational leadership also has some weaknesses. For example, it lacks conceptual clarity, another weakness relates to the measurement of transformational leadership. Some transformational factors are correlated with transactional and noninterventional leadership factors. It should also be noted that transformational leadership does not present clear assumptions about how leaders should act in specific situations. It focuses on ideals, inspiration, motivation, innovation and individual care.

During the same period, the researcher (Bass, 1985) proposed an even more sophisticated version of transformational leadership, which was based on the work of (House), but did not completely follow it. He believed that transformational leadership can be used in situations where the results are negative. He considered transactional and transformational leadership on the same line. (Avolio, 1999), in 1999, referred to transformational leadership as improving the performance of followers and realizing their full potential.

Transactional leadership includes all types of leadership that focus on agreement between leaders and followers. It encourages high performance through the use of rewards and punishments. When managers reward

subordinates for good performance and, conversely, punish them for poor performance, they increase the motivation of subordinates to ensure the desired action.

Charismatic leadership is often compared to transformational leadership. As mentioned in the previous subsection, charisma was first defined by (Weber, 1974)), who describes it as follows: "It is a personal characteristic that gives a person superhuman, outstanding power, it is not available to everyone, it is of divine origin, and as a result we get a person who is perceived as a leader. and treated as a leader. Later this theory was developed by (House, 1971). the personality characteristics of a charismatic leader developed by (House), which include: dominance, a strong desire to influence others, self-confidence, and belief in one's own moral values.

According to House's charismatic leadership theory, its face-to-face outcome is the follower's trust in the leader's ideology. Recognition of the leader without any doubts or questions.

Authentic leadership is one of the newest areas in leadership research. The theory focuses on how "real" and how authentic leadership is. There are several definitions of authentic leadership that explain it from different perspectives, they are: intrapersonal - processes taking place inside the leader's personality, self-knowledge, self-regulation, and self-evaluation; Developing - leadership behavior that is formed from the positive psychological characteristics and high quality of the leader. This is what is formed in people throughout life. Interpersonal - is built on relationships and involves achieving interactions between leaders and followers. It is a two-way process, as leaders influence followers and vice versa.

Today, one of the most recognized approaches in the field of leadership research is (House). The theory of conformity of means and ends. The essence of this theory lies in what the leader does to motivate subordinates to achieve the group and organization's goal. 1. Effective leaders clearly define the goals that subordinates are trying to achieve by working; 2. They reward subordinates according to the work done and the goal achieved and 3. They make clear the path that leads to the work goal. According to this theory, the steps a leader should take to motivate subordinates depend on both the subordinates and the type of work performed. In the theory of compatibility of the goal and the means, four behaviors of the leader are distinguished: 1. directive behavior; 2. Supportive behaviors; 3. complicity behavior; 4. Achievement-oriented behavior. Therefore, leaders must decide for themselves which behavior to use during the task to be performed by the subordinate in order to motivate them to perform the task.

Leadership concepts address the factors that leaders consider when applying leadership styles and overseeing an individual team. These principles focus on the ideas and perceptions about the qualities that leaders should have and how they should perform in the role of leader. In addition, leadership concepts help professionals understand what kind of skills and character traits they need to develop to advance in leadership roles.

The concepts of leadership differ from leadership theories in several ways. For example, leadership concepts generally serve as a guide for professionals to use in shaping leadership styles, communicating with teams, and leading processes. Leadership theories typically focus on the idea of using different methodologies, styles, and techniques when leading a team. Leadership concepts include different styles, qualities, and principles of employee team management approaches. Essentially, leadership concepts are based on various theories of management, and these qualities serve as the standard for effective managers, leaders, and other positional leaders. In addition, leadership concepts form the basis of standard management style and behavior theories and often include traits such as personality and character, initiative, motivation, influence, decision-making ability.

According to the studies by (Kirkpatrick, S.A. and Locke, E.A, 1991) have identified six traits that distinguish leaders from others. These are: Attitude, motivation, honesty, self-confidence, cognitive abilities and knowledge of the case. They think people with similar traits can be born or acquired over a lifetime They are. These 6 traits are exactly the traits that leaders need. These qualities of a leader distinguish people from each other and therefore, these differences are an important part of the leadership process. Also, empirical research (Peter G Northouse, 2010) conducted in the 1990s has shown that with social intelligence comprehension of feelings, behavior, and thoughts related traits are important traits for an effective leader.

The discussion of leadership as a trait has aroused great interest among foreign scholars. (Bryman, A, 1992) and an analysis by (Ellinger, A. D, 1986) found that personal qualities are closely related to a person's views on leadership. Even according to (Kirkpatrick, S.A. and Locke, E.A, 1991) effective leaders with distinctive qualities in some respects there are people. It is interesting to note that in the 1990s leadership as a trait became the subject of special attention to those for researchers who are distinguished by visionary, or charismatic leadership. These are: (Bass, B. M. , 1985), (Burton Nanus, Warren G. Bennis, 1985), (David A. Nadler, 1989)

It will not be uninteresting to discuss all those theories and systematic research devoted to the topic of leadership and identifying the characteristics of prominent leaders, since, naturally, the achievements of great people lead to universal recognition.

Followers of **The Trait Theory** as the starting point of leadership consider the individual characteristics of a leader and try to study the leader through these characteristics. This approach known as The Great Man Theory. This theory was formulated by Scottish philosopher, writer and teacher Thomas Carlyle. The theory is based on two main assumptions: 1) Great leaders are born, they have certain qualities that allows a person to be guided, guided and to be promoted; 2) Great leaders emerge when their need arises exists. Significant research and agreement have been reached today that leadership comes from a combination of both theories - and more. As already mentioned, there is a wide selection of qualities and characteristics of a leader. The

University of Santa Clara and the Tom Peters Group identified the following leadership characteristics: Honesty - Show sincerity, integrity and sincerity in all your actions. Deceptive behavior does not inspire confidence. Competent - base your actions on common sense and moral principles. Do not make decisions based on childish emotional desires or feelings. Prudent - Set goals and have a vision for the future. The vision should be owned by the entire organization. Effective leaders see what they want and how to get it. They usually choose priorities based on their core values. Inspiring - Show confidence in everything you do. By displaying mental, physical and spiritual endurance you inspire others to reach new heights. Take responsibility if necessary. Intelligent - Read, study and search for difficult tasks. Righteous Thinker - Treat all people fairly. Superstition is the enemy of justice. Show empathy for the feelings, values, interests, and well-being of others. Broad thinking - seek diversity. Brave - have the patience to achieve the goal, despite seemingly insurmountable obstacles. Exercise self-confidence in times of stress. Direct - Use common sense to make the right decisions at the right time. Imaginative - Make timely and appropriate changes in your thinking, plans and methods. Show creativity by thinking of new and better goals, ideas and problems. (John Whitehead, 2016)

Leadership theories study the qualities of effective leaders, including the qualities of effective and influential leaders, patterns of behavior, and actions. Leadership theories focus on explaining what makes good leaders by focusing on different behaviors and qualities that professionals can develop to become good leaders. While the concepts of leadership are qualities in themselves, leadership theories are the study and explanation of these qualities and their impact on professionals and their work environment.

Do not lose sight of the fact that there is no one type of leadership that is universally good or desirable. Organizations are characterized by their complexity, and therefore they can undergo changes at various and different rates, so you need to know how to adapt to momentary requirements; This also happens through his leadership, through the distribution of roles, etc. In

all cases, the truth is that a leader is not a leader by tenure: leadership is exercised, it is not inherited, something you place in an organization chart.

References:

1. Avolio, B. J. (1999). Full leadership development: Building the vital forces in organizations. Thousand Oaks.
2. Bass, B. M. . (1985). Leadership and performance beyond expectations. New York: Free Press.
3. Bass, B. M. (1985). Leadership and performance beyond expectations. . New York: Free Press.
4. Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. . (2006). Transformational leadership. . Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
5. Bryman, A. (1992). Charisma and Leadership in Organization. London: Sage Publications.
6. Burton Nanus, Warren G. Bennis. (1985). Leaders: Strategies for Taking Charge. Harper & Row.
7. Burton Nanus, Warren G. Bennis. (2006). Leaders: Strategies for Taking Charge. . New York: HarperCollins Publisher.
8. David A. Nadler. (1989). The Management of Organizations: Strategies. New York: Harper and Row.
9. Ellinger, A. D. (1986). A definitional examination of 'coaching,' 'organization development,' and 'human resource development'. Leadership & Organization Development Journal.
10. Gates, Bill. (n.d.). Retrieved from forbes.com: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kevinkruse/2013/04/09/what-is-leadership/?sh=391dce1d5b90#2fbb706713e1>;
11. House, R. (1971). Path-Goal theory. .
12. John Whitehead. (2016, 09 16). <https://johnkwhitehead.ca/three-theories-leadership/>. Retrieved from <https://johnkwhitehead.ca/three-theories-leadership/>.
13. Kirkpatrick, S.A. and Locke, E.A. (1991). Leadership Do Traits Matter. Lexington: Lexington Books.
14. Peter G Northouse. (2010). leadership theory and practice. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications .
15. Peter Guy Northouse. (2010). Introduction to Leadership: Concepts and Practice. SAGE 2007.
16. Weber. (1974). Leadership style. .